

Initial Study to Create a Sensation of Wetness by Combined Temperature and Vibration Stimuli

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Abstract. This paper introduces a haptic illusion by combining temperature and vibration stimuli to create a sensation of wetness. Sixteen participants took part in a case study, where three different humidity stimuli were introduced, two of them were real alongside the artificially created illusion. The results showed that the participants could not clearly distinguish between a real wet stimulus and the one made by the illusion.

Keywords: Humidity information · Haptic illusion · Thermo Electric Cooler

1 Introduction

Haptic feedback sensation enriches the user experience, especially in haptic-enhanced telemanipulation systems [1]. Whereas systems today mainly focus on providing technical stimuli directly linked to the interaction, such as vision, and tactile, the inclusion of ambient information is crucial for improved immersion in AR and VR applications. A research gap persists in the integration of haptic feedback in combination with temperature and humidity sensation. This paper focuses on the use of humidity information to create a tactile illusion of wetness.

Few studies discussed the humidity aspect in haptic systems. *Bentley et al.* [2] conducted an experiment, where participants were asked to dip their finger into water while it was covered with a rubber sheath, the participants felt coldness and light pressure even though no water droplets touched their skin. The authors' hypothesis is wetness is perceived by combining pressure and cold.

2 Technical setup

The humidity perception could be composed of temperature and vibration [2][3]. For temperature ranges, the humidity is introduced as a cold sensation to the skin [4], meaning 2 – 4 °C below the neutral temperature zone of the human body (30 – 36 °C).

Dew point temperature indicates the humidity feeling [6]. Eq. 1 correlates the dew point temperature T_d with the ambient temperature T and the relative humidity RH [5]. Pressure sensation is considered to be light in the range of 0.5 g, while heavy pressure can be resembled by 6 g vibration .

$$T_d \approx T - \frac{100 - RH}{5} \quad (1)$$

To apply the required temperature on the skin, a Thermoelectric Cooling (TEC) device (TEC1 127 05), is connected to a microcontroller (Arduino Uno), and an H-bridge (L298), Fig. 1. A closed-loop controller is used with a temperature sensor (DS18B20+) attached to the TEC. The tactile feedback is created using an ERM actuator (ERM 1003CA, Grewus GmbH).

Fig. 1. Technical setup arrangement on the forearm

2.1 Initial Case Study

An initial case study was performed on 16 participants (8 Males, and 8 Females, with an age range of 18-45 years). Two experiments were done. In the first experiment, the participants were blindfolded and were introduced to three different stimuli on their forearms. First to a non-active TEC wrapped inside a dry cloth, next to a non-active TEC wrapped inside a wet cloth at 22 °C. Finally, they were introduced to an active TEC at 20 °C and a vibration signal of around 0.5 g at a frequency of 30 Hz. The reason behind, wrapping the TEC inside the cloth in the first two stimuli, is to have the same weight on the participant's forearm in all the stimuli. The duration of each phase was 5 s. They were asked to sort their sensation during the three phases from the warmest/coldest and from the dry/wet. In the second experiment, the participants were introduced to an active TEC at 20°C and three different vibration levels (low at 45 Hz 0.9 g, medium at 125 Hz 2.8 g, high at 160 Hz 6.1 g). They were asked whether the change of the vibration shifted their focus more on the humidity perception or the level of coldness.

3 Results

Experiment 1 (Fig. 2) showed that participants could state which stimulus was dry or driest. There was no confusion being made with any of the wet conditions. Interestingly, both the real wet condition and the combination of coldness and vibration created a wet and wettest sensation. This unclear differentiation between the second and third stimuli indicates the suggested concept of transcoding by means of a combination of coldness and mechanical vibration.

The results of experiment 2 (Fig. 3) were not as distinct. A middle level of vibration at 125 Hz, 2.8 g was for the majority of participants creating an average humidity perception without specific bias towards "more humid" or "more cold". The decrease or increase of

vibration stimuli did not have a relevant impact, besides the fact that a perceptual shift was observed but without a specific tendency to either sensation.

Fig. 2. Results of Exp. 1, the confusion of the participants between the different stimuli

Fig. 3. Results of Exp. 2, effect of increasing the vibration level on the perception of coldness and humidity

4 Summary

The results of the case study showed an unclear distinction from the participants between the real wet situation and the illusion created with the active TEC. However, the change in the vibration stimuli didn't have an impact on the perception of wetness. For the next steps, the suggested concept could be tested in other case studies in comfortable humidity zones for more validation.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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